

**ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) IN ENTREPRENEURSHIP
EDUCATION AS PANACEA TO BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT AND SELF-RELIANCE**

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Abstract

This paper stresses the use of language and communication in enhancing successful business productivity in entrepreneurship, and to equip the youths and individuals with the skills that will enable them to be self-reliant. ESP enables one to look more closely at language and how it fulfils its main purpose, which is communication. Language has a powerful influence over people and their behavior. This is true mostly in the field of marketing and advertising in the business world. The researchers emphasize the language of advertising using Searle's Act Theory as the framework. The paper also examined some sampled advertisement marketing skills, attributes of an entrepreneur and entrepreneurship education. It is recommended that the young entrepreneurs should be taught specific language channelled to showcase their products, or skills so as to be successful in their businesses, also to be self-reliant. It is also recommended that government should review the implementation challenges of the entrepreneurship education in Nigerian schools, especially where it has gone moribund. Entrepreneurship education should move from theory to practice in schools.